

RISIS

RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE FOR SCIENCE
AND INNOVATION POLICY STUDIES

WP 9 / Task 1.1 Conceptual Framework EUPRO DEEPENING (NATPRO) DRAFT

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1 Introduction

[EUPRO](#) is a core facility to investigate structure, dynamics and impacts of [project](#)-based R&D collaboration to grasp and understand the development of the [European Research Area \(ERA\)](#). Advanced research in this direction needs constant EUPRO updates, but also extensions to other transnational and national research funding activities.

NATPRO addresses this gap

- by providing a systematic information basis on [nationally funded R&D projects](#), and
- by focussing on specific national funding programmes and selected countries depending on data availability.

NATPRO extension will be able to respond to interesting policy questions, such as

- the relation between national and [European funding](#), in terms of thematic complementarity and/or organisational overlapping;
- structure and dynamics of multi-level networks, featuring nodes (organisations) acting at the national level, at the European level, or at both levels ('gatekeeper'); and
- relationships between a set of characteristics of organisations and their ability to attract national vs. European funding.

2 Conceptual approach

2.1 Background

With its original focus on Europe, [EUPRO](#) has become one of the main assets of empirical research investigating structure and dynamics of publicly funded R&D collaboration networks across the European territory (see Scherngell 2019 for an overview). However, in a policy context we can observe a debate on the interplay between European and national funding endeavours and its impacts on observed collaboration structures at different spatial levels. Moreover, the question whether knowledge transmitted through European networks can be diffused within countries – leveraged by nationally funded collaborative R&D – is high on the research agenda.

Against this background, we have chosen to follow the demand both from policy and the scientific community to **advance EUPRO in a direction to integrate R&D projects funded by national R&D funding channels, the so-called NATPRO module**. Given that national R&D funding systems are well endowed, and in magnitude of funding usually exceed the amount of European funding, this is a very effortful exercise that can only be addressed using existing [RISIS](#) resources, e.g. in terms of name matching (with RISIS registers), geocoding or topical assignment.

As in EUPRO as a whole, the main approach of the NATPRO extension is to collect data from the publicly available data sources from the web. This requires identifying national research funding organisations (RFOs), to screen the public availability of project data, and to evaluate potential alternatives (e.g. data collection via national contact persons in RFOs or public authorities). During the first 18 months of the project, a *pilot phase* for the NATPRO extension including five countries, **Austria, Czech Republic, Estonia, Germany and Italy, was successfully completed**.

Main public data sources providing data on national R&D funding are:

- [OpenAire](#)
- [National research information system \(NRIS\)](#)
- Public databases on R&D projects provided by individual [Research funding organisations \(RFO\)](#)

Additionally, RFOs usually have additional internal databases. In case the public available data is not sufficient, extracts from these internal databases can serve as a substitute for data that is

- not at all available, or
- does not cover all core variables and/or
- main programmes or time periods (e.g. older data).

A specific effort will be done to cover [new Member States from Central and Eastern European countries \(NMS\)](#). In this respect, an analysis of the R&D policies in New Member States (NMS) in terms of a characterisation of the changing policy landscape of R&D policies and the identification and description of research funding structures and organisations is done. This analysis resulted in a working paper on R&D policies in NMS (<https://zenodo.org/record/3906234>), summarising the governance of R&D policy, the R&D funding structure (national funds, structural funds, international funding) and data availability for each NMS. The first version of this working paper (Q2 2019) was a main input for definition of pilot countries from the NMS and the final version will also be the systematic base for the data collection in additional NMS from Q3 2020 onwards.

Different access conditions and the existence of [NRIS](#) in turn implies different strategies not only for data collection but also the transformation of unchanged raw data into the NATPRO database

structure and variables (separate tables for projects, participations and programmes). The process of data collection and transformation is followed for each source dataset by a process of data cleaning (e.g. organisation names) and semi-automated name matching to [OrgReg](#)¹ and [FirmReg](#)². In course of this process, the established tools and processes of EUPRO are adapted to the needs of NATPRO. All findings from the actual data collection and the transformations performed are systematically documented country-by-country in a data report.

Core data (see section 2.2.1) focuses on the data needed to trace organisation by organisation networks. Additional information (see section 2.2.2) should cover the topic of the project, and – where applicable – project costs, funding instruments and funding calls. NATPRO will also collect national data (see section 2.2.3), which is only available for specific [RFOs](#) or countries, in a non-standardised way.

The focus of NATPRO is on collaborative [R&D projects](#), defined as **research projects with at least two different research or other organisations participating**. Therefore, only instruments including such collaborative R&D projects have to be included. However, NATPRO does not systematically assess funding instruments in terms of this criteria, the exclusion is therefore optional.

Figure 1: EUPRO and NATPRO within RISIS

2.2 Core data, additional data and national data

NATPRO distinguishes between core, additional and national data. While this section provides an overview for all data and variable to be collected within each category, the technical specification of the NATPRO variables is provided in section 5.2.

¹ Lepori, B. (2020), A register of public-sector research organizations as a tool for research policy studies and evaluation. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3751213>

² Camerani, R., Caldarola, B., & Guerini, M. (2020), RISIS FirmReg - Objectives, Perimeter and Main Functionalities. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3906560>

2.2.1 Core data

Core data is the data **needed for each RFO / NRIS for inclusion**. Data availability and quality must be assessed for each country before data collection can be started. Core data will be available in a **cleaned and harmonised** way.

2.2.2 Additional data

Additional data is **not needed for inclusion**. However, additional data may be needed in cases of missing core data (in particular for geo localisation). Additional data will be available in a **cleaned and harmonised** way.

2.2.3 National data

National data is all other data available and (potentially) useful for **analysis on national levels but beyond the scope of EUPRO**. While such national data can and will be collected and stored in the respective data base, data will **not be cleaned, enriched or harmonised**.

2.3 RFO and programme level data

All [RFO](#) and programme level data will be stored in the NATPRO programme table (see Table 2)

If the RFO is included in the EFIL and/or OrgReg database, users may derive (further) harmonised data from EFIL and/or OrgReg via the EFIL Instrument_ID, the EFIL RFO_ID and the OrgReg_ID (see 4.4).

2.3.1 Core data (programme_core)

Programme Name [prg]

List of programmes for each RFO as provided by the source dataset. **A list of included programmes is needed for each RFO** for the provision of a unique prg_id and in turn linking with project level data.

Funding Country [ctry]

Country and ISO Code (2 digit). **No missing allowed**.

Programme ID [prg_id]

Internal ID for each programme for linking with project table: ctry (2-digits) + rfo_acr + number(3-digits). If rfo_acr missing, the acronym of NRIS is used.

EFIL Instrument_ID [efil_instrument_ID]

If the programme is included in EFIL, the EFIL instrument ID will be used to enable linking on instrument level between NATPRO and EFIL (see section 4.4). Due to the different levels of granularity of source datasets and EFIL, multiple Programme ID (and Programme Name) may be linked to the same EFIL Instrument_ID.

EFIL RFO_ID [efil_rfo_id]

The EFIL RFO_ID is needed for linking with the EFIL database (see section 4.4) on the RFO level (if available),

OrgReg_ID [orgreg_id]

The OrgReg_ID for funding organisation (if applicable) will be added (see section 0)

RFO English Name [*rfo_name_orig*], RFO Official Name [*rfo_name_nat*] and RFO Acronym [*rfo_acr*]

The official English name of the research funding organisation, official name of the research funding organisation in national language and official Acronym of the research funding organisation as provided by the source dataset.

The availability of *rfo_name_orig* or *rfo_name_nat* or *rfo_acr_orig* is mandatory as this information is needed for the identification of unique RFOs as well as for linking with EFIL (see section 4.4) and/or OrgReg (see section 0) on the RFO level.

2.3.1 Additional data (*programme_add*)

Programme Name Acronym [*prg_acr*]

Official acronym of the programme (if available) as provided by the source dataset

Subprogramme Name [*subprg*]

Additional programme levels (if available) as provided by the source dataset. Information on sub programmes are not core data.

RFO Website [*rfo_url_orig*]

Official website of the research funding organisation (in English) as provided by the source dataset

RFO Classification [*rfo_type_orig*]

If RFO is included in EFIL database, the RFO classification provide by EFIL can be used via EFIL RFO_ID. For other RFOs, the RFO classification may be assigned using the classification provided below.

Table 1: RFO Classification

Level 1	Description	Level 2	Code
Governmental agencies	RFOs which are functionally part of the public administration, meaning for example divisions of ministries, ministerial committees, etc. Typical examples at the European level are DG Research (managing the European FP), at national level research ministries.	National research/science ministry	RFO0101
		National sector ministry (e.g. energy)	RFO0102
		Regional government (non-divided in subcategories)	RFO0103
Independent agencies	RFOs which have functionally a large degree of independence from the State in managing their activities and selecting the projects to be funded; in some cases, this might be realized by a specific legal status granting autonomy. A key criterion to distinguish the two types of agencies is, if the State (e.g. ministry) retains the right to take the final decision on granting money to specific projects.	Innovation agency , whose mission and funding are oriented towards innovation and creation of economic value	RFO0201
		Research council , who's funding is mainly oriented towards basic research and having strong connection to the academic community (for example in the composition of decision-making committees)	RFO0202
		Sectoral RFO – related to specific topics (energy, environment, etc.), e.g. sectoral regulatory agencies or sectoral funding agencies	RFO0203
		Intergovernmental agency created by international treaty (e.g. ESA)	RFO0204
		EU-implementation agency based on EU law (e.g. the agency managing AAL)	RFO0205
		International non-governmental association (European Science Foundation)	RFO0206
Performers	Organisations, whose main mission is to perform R&D activities, even if it might host some funding agencies activities	Public research organisations (PRO) assuming also a function in funding	RFO0301
		Private research organisations.	RFO0302

2.4 Project level data

2.4.1 Core data (projects_core)

All project core level data will be stored in the NATPRO project table (see Table 3).

National Project ID [project_id]

Unique identifier for each project in the source database (**needed for updating**). This identifier can either be the project ID provided by the [RFO](#) or by the [NRIS](#).

Programme ID (prg_id)

Internal ID for each programme for linking with programme table: ctry (2-digits) + rfo_acr + number(3-digits). If rfo_acr missing, the acronym of NRIS is used.

Programme Name [prg]

Programme as provided by the source dataset. **Needed for each project** for linking with programme table.

Start Date [start]

Day, month and year of project start (at least **year needed**). If only year available, set to January 1st of the year

End Date [end]

Day, month and year of project end (at least **year needed**). If only year available, set to December 31st of the Year

English Project Title [title]

Full title of the project in English as provided by source dataset. If not available, this variable can be added with automated translation.

2.4.2 Additional data (projects_add)

Project optional/additional data will be stored in the NATPRO project table (see Table 3).

Original Project Title [title_orig]

Full title of the project in national language as provided by the source dataset. **Only needed if no English title is available.**

Programme Acronym [prg_acr]

Abbreviation of the programme name

Project Acronym [proj_acr]

(Non-unique) project acronym or abbreviation of the project title

English Keywords [keywords]

Keywords in English as provided by the source dataset. Keywords will not be harmonised but only collected for further processing by users or textual searches.

Keywords in national language as provided by the source dataset. Keywords will not be harmonised but only collected for further processing by users or textual searches.

English Subject Areas [*subject_area*]

Subject Areas or similar information in English as provided by source dataset (e.g. FoS). FoS and other classifications will not be harmonised but only collected for further processing by users or textual searches.

Subject Areas [*subject_area_orig*]

Subject Areas or similar information in national language as provided by source dataset (e.g. FoS). FoS and other classifications will not be harmonised but only collected for further processing by users or textual searches.

English Objective / Abstract [*abstract*]

General information about the objectives of the project in English as provided by source dataset

Objective / Abstract [*abstract_orig*]

General information about the objectives of the project in national language as provided by source dataset

Call [*call*]

Different types of calls and specific calls. Calls will not be harmonised but only collected for further processing by users, textual searches or for calculating missing start dates (core variable).

Contract type [*contract_type*]

Different types of contracts which regulate size, financing and funding of the research projects. Contract types will not be harmonised but only collected for further processing by users or textual searches.

Project Cost [*project_cost*]

Official project costs; since not all projects are financed completely, figures in "Project Costs" are equal to or larger than figures in "Project Funding". Only costs for the total project will be stored as variable project cost, costs per year will be included in national data.

Project Funding [*project_funding*]

Financing contribution of the RFO; since not all projects are financed completely, figures in "Project Funding" are equal to or smaller than figures in "Project Cost". Only funding for the total project will be stored as variable project funding, funding per year will be included in national data.

Official website of the project

Project outcomes [project_outcome]

Deliverables, reports, patents, etc.

Project outcomes will not be harmonised but only collected for further processing by users or textual searches.

2.4.3 National data

National data refers to all other data available and (potentially) useful for analysis on national levels but beyond the scope of EUPRO. This includes for example information on project costs or funding per year. The included national data is documented on a country by country base in the respective section of the data report. For the pilot phase, all easily available information on the project level that is not core or additional data were collected and stored as national data. However, no effort (e.g. web scraping) will be used to collect this kind of data.

2.5 Participating organisations data

2.5.1 Core data (participations_core)

Participation core data will be stored in the NATPRO participation table (see Table 4)

National Project_ID [project_id]

See section 2.4, needed for linking with project level data

Organisation name [org_name]

Full names of all participating organisations as provided by source dataset (multiple spelling variants for the same organisation are possible)

OrgReg_ID [orgreg_id]

Link to [OrgReg](#) to be identified and integrated by semi-automated matching process

FirmReg_ID [firmreg_id]

Link to [FirmReg](#) to be identified and integrated by semi-automated matching process.

2.5.2 Additional data (participations_add)

Participation level additional data will be stored in the NATPRO project table (see Table 3).

Country [ctry]

Country of origin and ISO Code (2 digit)

Used if address information is provided in a structured way for street level information

Postal Code [pc]

Used if address information is provided in a structured way for postal code

City [city]

Used if address information is provided in a structured way for the city name

Full Address [full_address]

Used if address information is provided in an unstructured way by the source dataset

Original OrgType [org_type_orig]

As provided in the source dataset

Standardised organisation classification for organisations included in OrgReg/FirmReg will only be provided via OrgReg

Role [role]

Information on project lead/coordinator

Organisation URL [org_url]

Official website of the organisation

Participant funding [org_funding]

Financing contribution of the RFO per participant

2.5.3 National data

National data refers to all other data available and (potentially) useful for analysis on national levels but beyond the scope of EUPRO. While such national data can and will be collected and stored in the respective data base, data will not be cleaned, enriched or harmonised.

2.6 Entity Relationship Model

Each dataset ([RFO](#) or [NRIS](#)) on national funding within [EUPRO](#) is realized as an independent database which can be linked via [OrgReg](#) and [FirmReg](#) across different EUPRO modules and to other datasets within [RISIS](#). The relation between projects and participations is realised via a unique

identifier for each project within each database (Project_ID) and identical to the unique identifier for the respective source database.

For the technical specification of the entity relationship model see 5.3.

2.7 OrgReg and FirmReg as integrative dimension within EUPRO and to other RISIS datasets

Every Organisation name is linked via OrgReg_ID/FirmReg_ID in the participations table to RISIS-[OrgReg](#) (Register of European Public Research and Higher Education Actors)³ and [FirmReg](#) (Register of European Firms)⁴, which provide data on the legal seat (country) of the organisation, the organisation type, etc.

It should be noted that we only link to OrgReg/FirmReg, no raw data (e.g. organisation type) will be changed based on information available in OrgReg/FirmReg.

2.8 Direct linkage with EFIL (and SIPER) on programme level

For countries/RFOs included in NATPRO and the [EFIL](#) database, NATPRO can be linked to the two instruments' tables of the EFIL database, which store descriptors, respectively static and time-variant, on funding instruments, via the EFIL instrument ID. This commonly used instrument ID may also be used for direct linkage with SIPER⁵.

³ Lepori, B. (2020), A register of public-sector research organizations as a tool for research policy studies and evaluation. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3751213>

⁴ Camerani, R., Caldarola, B., & Guerini, M. (2020), RISIS FirmReg - Objectives, Perimeter and Main Functionalities. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3906560>

⁵ Wallwaey, E., & Bühner, S. (2019). Documentation of RISIS datasets: SIPER. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3374733>

Figure 2: [EFIL](#) internal structure and external connections, at a glance

3 Coverage

3.1 Selection of pilot countries

For the selection of pilot countries, the inclusion of at least two [NMS](#) and at least two larger EU member states was planned. Additionally, countries with and without national information systems ([NRIS](#)) on [R&D projects](#) should be included.

- Austria (no NRIS on R&D projects)
- Czech Republic (NMS with NRIS on R&D projects)
- Estonia (NMS with NRIS on R&D projects)
- Germany (large country without NRIS on R&D projects)
- Italy (large country without NRIS on R&D projects)

3.2 Future development

After the pilot phase, a second batch of countries to be included into NATPRO will be selected. The results of the NATPRO pilot phase are provided in the table below.

Table 1: NATPRO pilot phase

Country	Status of data collection	Number of Projects	Number of Participations	Overlap with OrgReg*	Time Coverage
Austria	Matched to OrgReg	17,331	24,581	16,395 (69%)	1995-2020 (FWF), 2015-2020 (FFG)
Czech Republic	Matched to OrgReg	37,848	62,214	44,041 (71%)	2000-2020
Estonia	Matched to OrgReg	3,583	4,156	3,704 (89%)	2000-2020
Germany	Matched to OrgReg	124,590	151,521	131,335 (87%)	1999-2020
Italy	Matched to OrgReg	9,977	42,111	41,918 (99.5%)	1999-2015 (PRIN programme)
Total	Matched to OrgReg	193,329	284,583	237,393 (83%)	

*participations covered by organisations included in OrgReg

3.3 Focus on collaborative R&D projects

The focus of NATPRO is on collaborative R&D projects (see section 2.1), defined as **research projects with at least two different research or other organisations participating**. Therefore, only instruments including such collaborative R&D projects have to be included and are the core of the NATPRO dataset.

However, NATPRO does not systematically assess funding instruments in terms of this criteria, the inclusion or exclusion of other, non-collaborative, R&D projects is therefore depending on the source dataset. Data on such other R&D projects is therefore included if easily available as additional data but excluded if specific efforts are needed for inclusion.

3.4 Time coverage

If available, data starting from 2000 will be collected. However, the **emphasis is on data from 2010 onwards**, in particular in terms of standardisation/cleaning. Data before 2010 will only be collected if readily available (e.g. csv download) and not if data collection has to be done by other means including web scraping. Data on R&D projects from up to 2009 is therefore included if easily available as additional data.

See data report for each country.

4 General data collection approach

4.1 Collection of raw data

As in EUPRO, the main approach of NATPRO will be to scrap data from publicly available data sources from the web. For countries with a national research information system ([NRIS](#)), data will be collected on a country-by-country basis. For all other countries, raw data collection will be done on the level of the identified main [RFO](#).

Data are, if needed, transformed into comma separated files (extension .csv) using UTF 8 codepage and the pipe “|” character as a field delimiter. Therefore, the pipe “|” will be removed from all raw data before any further data processing.

4.2 Setting up source datasets for each RFO or NRIS

Source data will remain mostly unchanged (structured mirror of source for each [RFO/NRIS](#)), minimally including:

- Programme table (see section 2.3)
- Project table (see section 2.4)
- Participations table (see section 2.5)

Section 5.2 provides the technical variable description for the three tables while section 5.3 illustrates the entity-relationship model for each NATPRO dataset.

4.3 Cleaning and matching of organisation name

In a next step, the organisation name is prepared by simple automated processing, e.g. elimination of punctuation, capitalisation, common abbreviations, metadata (e.g. departments, institutes...). Then, we apply specific matching algorithms based on statistical properties such as the frequency of adjacent characters in the organisation names to identify similar organisation names that can be attributed to organisations in [OrgReg/FirmReg](#). Finally, all algorithmically identified name matches are manually checked for accuracy.

4.4 Linking of programmes and RFOs to EFIL & OrgReg

If an RFO is included in the EFIL dataset, the EFIL instrument ID and EFIL RFO_ID can be added to the programme table to enable linking on instrument level between NATPRO and the EFIL database. Due to the different levels of granularity of the source datasets and EFIL (a single funding instrument in EFIL can group funding instruments that show similar characteristics and determining a “funding route”), multiple Programme ID may have the same EFIL Instrument_ID.

Furthermore, RFOs included in OrgReg can also be directly linked to OrgReg via the OrReg_ID included in the programme table (if applicable)

4.5 Linking of participants to OrgReg & FirmReg

The OrgReg_ID/FirmReg_ID of the identified organisation is added to the participations table. Information from [OrgReg/FirmReg](#) (e.g. OrgTyp) can be used to enrich national datasets (see also 2.7) and to link to other EUPRO modules as well as other RISIS datasets.

4.6 Regionalisation

In the NATPRO context, regionalisation is the assignment of geographical locations to European regions ([NUTS regions](#)). Organisations included in [OrgReg/FirmReg](#) can be geolocated using the locations provided in the registers.

For additional data regionalisation, RISIS developed geolocalisation tools can be used, specifying their geographical locations by giving their latitude and longitude coordination. This facilitates all kind of spatial analyses of project-based R&D networks, e.g. the investigation of the network at the level of functional urban areas. However, this is depending on availability of address data in source datasets (not core data).

4.7 Translation

Data is collected in English. If data is only available in the national language of the country, translation into English by using auto-translation tools may be used. This is in particular the case for the core variable “*English Project Title*” (title) based on the “*Original Project Title*” (title_orig).

4.8 Topical annotation

For topical annotation (e.g. [SGC](#) & [KET](#)), RISIS developed tools can be used.

5 Technical specifications

5.1 Information on the data base system

5.1.1 Current data base system used

The modules of the [EUPRO database](#) are currently realised as Microsoft Access 2016 databases.

5.2 Technical variable definition

Table 2: **Programme table** - Data type of variables providing information about funding organisations and programmes

Variable	Variable Name	Category	Data type	Remarks
prg_id	Programme ID	Link	Text	Link to project table (e.g. ATFFG001) (ATFWF001) on programme level
prg	Programme Name	Core	Text	if missing, prg_acr needed
ctry	Funding Country	Core	Text	ISO 2 digit (except UK for GB)
orgreg_id	OrgReg_ID	Link	Text	orgreg_id of funding organisation (if applicable)
efil_instrument_id	EFIL Instrument_ID	Link	Text	Provided by EFIL database (if available) for linking
efil_rfo_id	EFIL RFO_ID	Link	Text	Provided by EFIL database (if available) for linking
rfo_name	RFO English Name	Core	Text	rfo_name or rfo_name_nat or rfo_acr mandatory
rfo_name_nat	RFO Official Name in National Language		Text	
rfo_acr	RFO Acronym		Text	
prg_acr	Programme Name Acronym	Additional	Text	Needed if prg is missing
rfo_url	RFO Website	Additional	Link	
rfo_type	RFO Classification	Additional	Text	

Table 3: **Project table** - Data type of core and additional variables providing information about projects

Variable	Variable Name	Category	Data type	Remark
project_id	National Project_ID	Core	Text	unchanged national project ID, needed for updates and linking to national source dataset
prg_id	Programme ID	Link	Text	Link to programme table
start	Start Date	Core	Date	If only year available, set to January 1 st of the year
end	End Date	Core	Date	If only year available, set to December 31 st of the Year
title	English Project Title	Core	Long Text	English title as provided by source dataset. If not available, title in national language can be used and auto-translated.
title_nat	Project Title in National Language	Additional	Long Text	Original title as provided by source dataset, needed if no English Title is available
proj_acr	Project Acronym	Additional	Text	
keywords	English Keywords	Additional	Long Text	Freely chosen
keywords_nat	Keywords in National Language	Additional	Long Text	Freely chosen
subject_areas	English Subject Areas	Additional	Long Text	Any pre-defined categories as provided by source dataset (e.g. FoS)
subject_areas_nat	Subject Areas in National Language	Additional	Long Text	Any pre-defined categories as provided by source dataset (e.g. FoS) in national language
abstract	English Abstract / Objective	Additional	Long Text	
abstract_nat	Abstract / Objective in National Language	Additional	Long Text	
call	Call	Additional	Text	
contract_type	Contract Type	Additional	Text	
project_cost	Project Cost	Additional	Number	
project_funding	Project Funding	Additional	Number	
project_url	Project URL	Additional	Link	

Table 4: Participation table - Data type of core and additional variables providing information about participations

Variable	Variable Name	Category	Data type	Remarks
project_id	National Project_ID	Link	Text	link to project table
org_name_nat	Organisation name	Core	Text	as given in the source data set
orgreg_id	OrgReg_ID	Link	Text	If applicable
firmreg_id	FirmReg_ID	Link	Text	If applicable
ctry	Country	Additional	Text	ISO 2 digit
address	Address	Additional	Text	
pc	Postal Code	Additional	Text	
city	City	Additional	Text	
full_address	Full Address	Additional	Long Text	
org_type_nat	OrgType	Additional	Text	organisation type as given in the source data set
role	Role	Additional	Text	Information on project lead / coordinator
org_url	Organisation URL	Additional	Link	Official website of the organisation
org_funding	Participant funding	Additional	Number	Financing contribution of the RFO per participant

5.3 Description of the Entity Relationship Model

Figure 3: Schematic data structure

5.4 Technical information on interfaces with other infrastructures

Integration of EUPRO within [RISIS](#) has been core in order to increase the scientific value of EUPRO for cross-dataset empirical analyses, on the one hand, and to be able to gain from RISIS developed facilities, such as geolocalisation tools, for the further advancement of EUPRO, on the other hand. Inter-operability with other datasets is considered as a key element for the further establishment and sustainable attractiveness of EUPRO for new research endeavours, in particular those relating to the investigation of impacts of publicly funded R&D networks.

5.5 Integration with RCF

The EUPRO version that is made available for access to researchers in RISIS is foreseen to be fully incorporated in [RISIS Core Facility](#) (RCF), under the condition of controlled access and that security of usage is given (i.e. access for selected users with a concrete research project to the parts of the dataset needed for the research). Note that underlying cleaning and harmonisation data (e.g. name variants) will not be made available via RCF. Linking to other datasets in the RCF will be realized via the RISIS registers (providing the respective identifiers to the registers in EUPRO). Technical issues for incorporation of EUPRO into RCF (e.g. database system, how can a user access which parts of the dataset, etc.) are to be defined in close cooperation with WP4.

[to be completed]

- **EFIL:** [RISIS](#) dataset on public R&D funding instruments
- **ERA:** [European Research Area](#)
- **ETER:** [European Tertiary Education Register](#)
- **EU:** [European Union](#)
- **EUPRO** (see also [European projects](#)): Projects and participants database constructed and maintained by *AIT Austrian Institute of Technology*.
- **European projects:** [EUPRO](#) has been developed by AIT Austrian Institute of Technology and comprises systematic information on R&D projects and all participating organisations funded by the European Framework Programmes (FP). It covers information on: projects (such as project objectives and achievements, project costs, total funding, start and end date, contract type, information on the call) and details of participating organisations.
- **FirmReg:** [RISIS](#) firms register used in combination with the register of public-sector organizations ([OrgReg](#)) for the identification of Standardized actors . The perimeter includes all firms covered by the three RISIS database Corporate Innovation Board ([CIB](#)), [VICO](#) and [Cheetah](#) Database (Database on Fast Growing Medium Sized Firms). The FirmReg firms are either individual firms or the group-level entity – Global Ultimate Owner (GUO) or Industrial Global Ultimate Owner (GUOI), when the GUO is not an industrial company.
- **FoS:** [Fields of Science](#)
- **FP** (see also [European projects](#)): [European Framework Programmes for Research and Innovation](#)
- **KET:** [Key Enabling Technologies](#). KETs are a group of six technologies: micro and nanoelectronics, nanotechnology, industrial biotechnology, advanced materials, photonics, and advanced manufacturing technologies. They have applications in multiple industries and help tackle societal challenges. Countries and regions that fully exploit KETs will be at the forefront of creating advanced and sustainable economies.
- **National projects:** [EUPRO](#) will be expanded by AIT Austrian Institute of Technology to include systematic information on [R&D projects](#) and all participating organisations funded by national RFOs. It covers information on: projects (such as project objectives and achievements, project costs, total funding, start and end date, contract type, information on the call) and details of participating organisations.
- **NMS:** New Member States from Central and Eastern European countries: Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech Republic, Estonia, Hungary, Latvia, Poland, Romania, Slovakia and Slovenia.
- **NRIS** (see also National projects): National research information system
- **NUTS regions:** The [NUTS classification](#) (Nomenclature of territorial units for statistics) is a hierarchical system for dividing up the economic territory of the EU and the UK
- **OpenAire:** [European Open Science Infrastructure, for open scholarly and scientific communication](#)
- **OrgReg:** [RISIS](#) register of public-sector organizations used in combination with the RISIS firms register ([FirmReg](#)) for the identification of Standardized actors . They include Higher Education Institutions, Public Research Organizations, Private-Non-Profit Research Organizations, Research Hospitals and Public Administration entities involved in research. The total number of entities involved is expected to be around 5,000, including however a large number of entities with no or very few research outputs. OrgReg provides for stable IDs for these organizations, as well as for tracking demographic changes over time. Orgreg also provides some basic descriptive information including the organizational type, geographical location, foundation year and the whole demography from the year 2000 onwards. For Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) data on revenues, staff, students are

available from the [European Tertiary Education Register \(ETER\)](#), but limited to the years 2008, 2011-2014. For other public entities, data availability is far more uncertain.

- **RCF:** [RISIS](#) Core Facility
- **RFO:** Research funding organisation
- **RISIS** (see also [OrgReg](#) and [FirmReg](#)): *Research Infrastructure for Science and Innovation (policy) Studies*.
- **RTDI:** Research, Technological Development, and Innovation
- **SGC:** [Societal Grand Challenges](#)
- **SIPER:** [Science and Innovation Policy Evaluations Repository \(SIPER\)](#) is a rich and unique database and knowledge source of science and innovation policy evaluations worldwide. SIPER provides on-line access to [STI](#) evaluation reports as well as data on the underlying policy measures at a single location.
- **Standardised actors** are those actors subject to process of standardisation across the database and that are identified through stable identifiers set in the RISIS register of public-sector organisations ([OrgReg](#)), respectively the RISIS firms register ([FirmReg](#)). These actors are therefore identified uniquely across data sources.
- **STI:** Science, technology and innovation

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